

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON INTER-YARN FRICTION CHARACTERISTICS OF KEVLAR FABRICS WITH DIFFERENT MASS CONCENTRATIONS OF STF

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ABSTRACT

Shear thickening fluid (STF) is a suspension solution, the viscosity of which increases with the shear rate. The Kevlar fabric treated by STF showed the improvement of impact resistance at high speed. The STF-Kevlar fabrics have a good application prospect in the fan casing containment system of aeroengine. In the current paper, three types of STF suspension was prepared using spherical SiO₂ particles of 750 nm diameter in different weight concentration to impregnate the Kevlar49 fabrics. The rheological properties of different STF were investigated. Yarn pull-out tests were conducted to figure out the effect of STF on the friction behavior of fabrics which exert significant influence on the impact resistance. the corresponding force displacement curves are obtained, and the static and dynamic friction coefficient between yarns were analyzed. It was concluded that the yarn pull-out force of the STF-Kevlar fabrics is much higher than neat Kevlar fabrics. The force required for the corresponding yarn to be pulled out increase with the concentration of STF increases while it is barely affected by the yarn pull-out rate. Correspondingly, the friction coefficients are also affected positively by the particle weight concentration. The higher the concentration of STF-Kevlar fabric, the greater the dynamic and static friction coefficients between yarns.

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YARN PULL-OUT TESTS OF STF-KEVLAR FABRICS

The yarn pull-out test was carried out on INSTRON 2344 test machine with maximum load bearing capacity of 2 KN.

- Clamping the pull-out specimen on the testing machine. The length of the yarn fixed by the upper end clamp is 3 cm, and the size of the fabric fixed by the lower end clamp is 8 cm × 2 cm. The length of the yarn sliding over the fabric is 9 cm.
- The three previously marked yarns were pulled out from the fabric with the same loading rate of 50mm/min for neat Kevlar and three different concentration STF-Kevlar fabrics, and the corresponding load-displacement curves were obtained.
- The pull-out tests were carried out at loading rate of 500 mm/min again and another set of data were obtained for 4 types of fabrics.
- The comparison of the testing fabrics before and after the pull-out test.

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TEST RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

It is found that the dynamic and static friction coefficients of the neat Kevlar fabrics are relatively small between 0.09 and 0.16. The dynamic and static friction coefficients of Kevlar fabrics treated with STF are obviously lifted to range of 0.2~0.45. The value of friction coefficients increases significantly, reaching the percentage more than 100% and 200% at most. Furthermore, with the increase of STF concentration, the friction coefficients between the warp and fill yarns of STF-Kevlar fabrics also increase significantly. On the contrary, the yarn pull-out rate has little effect on the friction coefficient between the yarns. Particularly, compared with 70% STF-Kevlar, the dynamic and static friction coefficients of 72% STF-Kevlar fabrics decrease at 50 mm/min yarn pull-out rate. The abnormal phenomena could be caused by the incomplete impregnation of fabrics in 72wt% STF solution, which resulted in the SiO₂ particles not completely attached to the fiber.

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CONCLUSIONS

In the current paper, the inter-yarn friction characteristics were investigated on neat Kevlar fabric and STF-Kevlar fabrics of three different concentrations. The variation of stress-modulus and viscosity-modulus were obtained through rheological properties tests. Three types of STF-Kevlar fabrics were obtained by immersing by the prepared STF solution. The yarn pull-out tests were carried out and compared for neat Kevlar fabrics and three types of STF-Kevlar fabrics. The main conclusions were drawn as follows:

- The critical shear rate of three types STF is relatively close at about 1/s while the maximum viscosity is influenced significantly by the mass concentration. The maximum viscosity could be 20 times higher when the mass concentration increases by only 5%.
- The yarn pull-out force of the STF-Kevlar fabrics is much higher than neat Kevlar fabrics. The force required for the corresponding yarn to be pulled out increase with the concentration of STF increases in principle while it is barely affected by the yarn pull-out rate.
- The friction coefficients between yarns of neat Kevlar fabric is much lower than STF-Kevlar fabrics. The friction coefficients are also affected positively by the particle weight concentration. The higher the concentration of STF-Kevlar fabric, the greater the dynamic and static friction coefficients between the yarns.